

KEY COMPONENTS OF HIGH TEMPERATURE STABLE HIGH OXIDATION RESISTANT CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES OF SiC/SiC TYPE WORKING OUT AND TECHNOLOGICAL WAYS OF THEIR MAKING

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SUMMARY: In a short form the grounding of the task priority is given. Necessity of complex key components of ceramic matrix composites (CMC): polymer precursors, fibers and interface coatings - working out is the important line in this area. Some positive new results in the chemistry and technology of high temperature stable high oxidation resistant CMC for civil aviation and automotive industry have been received. The easy production process of oxygenless polycarbosilane has been developed, high pressure and oxygenated initiators were not used. A new method to synthesise oxygenless polymetallo-carbosilanes (PMCS) to stabilize ceramic fine structure has been proposed and preliminary checked. New PMCS having metals in cluster form (nano-particles) without any oxygen links between metal and silicon atoms are called cluster polymetallo-carbosilanes (CIPMCS). They have improved structure and are cheaper in making also. Preliminary research stages in oxygenless polymer curing with unsaturated organosilicon compounds and complex interface molybdenum disilicide - silicon carbide coatings have been carrying out. They have made possible to get specimen fiber with - 0,3%O₂ and 0,1-5% of Ti or Zr and have shown some perspectives in more economical technology and better oxidation resistance.

KEYWORDS: oxygenless ceramic polymer precursors, cluster polymetallo-carbosilanes, unsaturated curing organosilicons, tetravinylsilane, molybdenum disilicide, interface coating

INTRODUCTION

A high temperature stable high oxidation resistant CMC for a long work at 1500 – 1700°C in civil aviation and automotive engines is a subject of priority working out nowadays [1]. From working temperature 1100-1200 (now maximum) to 1500-1700°C transition make it possible to decrease fuel consumption and increase flight distant by 25% and to duplicate specific thrust. Cooling systems in some cases become unnecessary and in Diesel engine as well (adiabatic cycle) and so on [2,3]. One of good potential variants is CMC of SiC/SiC type with coreless SiC fiber. Unfortunately all components of this material now known: polymer

precursors, commercial (Nicalon and Tyranno) and pilot (radiation or unsaturated organic vapour curing) grade fibers, matrix compositions and structures, interface coatings - can not support work for a long time at temperatures more than 1100°C and too expensive. It is necessary to delete oxygen in all the components, to stabilize fine ceramic structure at high working temperatures, to work out very high oxidation resistant complex interface coating. It is very important to depreciate the production of components and the material on the whole. This aspects are the subjects of many publications and have been intensely discussed at the last international conferences (ICCM-9, ICCM-10, HT-CVC-1, HT-CMC-II, MICC-93) in 1993-96. There is a wide range of difficult problems to overcome. The authors think especially important to work out all key components of this material in the frame of one complex program as for example it is not possible to develop oxygen resistant interface coating or rational stabilizing methods without well finished oxygenless fiber. This is a base for their research program and this paper.

MAIN LINES OF RESEARCH AND RESULTS

Polymer Precursors

PCS was first synthesized on the 70-th [4] by pyrolysis and thermal rearranging of polydimethyl silane (PDMS) in autoclave in inert environment (10 MPa, 470°C). This method is too expensive for industrial production. A lot of attempts to avoid high pressure and PDMS using through the help of initiators and other organosilicon compounds have not given positive results as far as PCS quality is concerned. The oxygen is introduced with initiators and stoichiometry and structure composition of PCS is distorted (Fig.1).

*Fig.1. MWD of synthesized PCS
1-high pressure, 2-low pressure, boron
initiated, 3- low pressure, titanium initiated,
4- low pressure without initiators*

*Fig.2. Iron cluster particle distribution by
size in high pressure polyethylene.
Content of Fe,%mas. 1-0,7; 2-1,0;
3-5,0;4-7,0 (model system)*

It is the studying of PDMS and PCS syntheses, chemical composition and molecular structure of initial and final products that have given the optimal regime in the temperature-pressure-

time-composition system. This regime makes it possible not to use oxygen containing initiators and any exotic initial products and to have as good PCS as autoclave one at handy temperature, pressure and process duration (Table 1). A considerable depreciation of PCS is reached which as is known becomes then 3- fold much in fibre and (4-5)- fold much in the composite production.

Table 1: Polymer precursors characteristics

Characteristics	[HSiC ₃]/ [SiC ₄]	Content, % mass.			MWD		
		O ₂	H at Si	Init.(metal)	M _n	M _w	M _z
PCS autoclav.	0,9-0,95	0,3 - 0,8	0,65 - 0,75	–	830	1310	2290
PBCS	0,8-0,85	1,0 - 3,0	0,55 - 0,65	0,5 - 1,0	1050	3010	9100
PTiCS	0,2-0,3	4,0 - 6,0	0,30 - 0,60	≤ 5,0	890	7300	250000
PCS(without in.)	0,9-0,93	0,3 - 0,8	0,60 - 0,70	–	1060	2070	4830
CIPMCS	0,95-1,1	< 0,5	0,92 - 0,98	0,5 - 5,0	1220	1830	3580

Ceramic Phase Structure Stabilizers, Polymetallo-carbosilanes

As it is generally known effective stabilizers of fine ceramic structure are hetero-atoms of many elements oxygen and nitrogen as well. By-effects such as fusibility, thermal stability, sintering ability and so on changing are positive using high melting metals (Ti, Zr, Hf, B, Mo and some other). The problem is working out of a method to introduce the metal into the polymer providing with the homogeneous distribution just on the synthesis stage and disusing of oxygen. The first demand was only fulfilled in the practical method of metal-stabilizers introducing through tetraalkoxi-compounds of metals. The «Tyranno» - fiber of Ube Industries (Japan) was made with tetraalkoxititan. But ceramic phase in this fiber is of Si-C-O-Ti type as Si-O-Ti link (oxygen bridge) takes place. More over active Si-H - links valuable for curing are spent in this reaction. So it is necessary to work out essential new way of metal introducing in the PCS or new method of PMCS synthesis.

The last task is carrying out by the authors on the base of an experience of linear monophase metallopolymers making: polyethylene, polypropylene, polytetrafluorethylene [5]. It is quite different from traditional methods to introduce metal particles of 5-100 μm in size into polymer to form homogenized and aggregatively stable but two-phase systems. Two-phase metallopolymers do not have so high physical and mechanical properties as initial polymer because their ordering (crystallinity) become lower. They cannot be used for spinning fiber also.

The new method introduce the metals in cluster form into micro voids which is natural in every polymer. These voids are connected with polymer molecules packing and located between crystalline and amorphous parts of micro volumes. Clusters (nano-particles) of metals are formed in situ as a result of high velocity thermodestruction of organometallic compound solutions during their input in polymer solutions or melts [6]. Carbonyls, acetates, phormiates and some other classes of metal compounds are applicable. Fig. 2 gives a notion of the method possibility. It shows Fe particles size distribution (small angle scattering of X-ray (XSAS)) in the high pressure polyethylene at different general metal concentrations. In the most interesting for ceramic stabilization 1-3% Fe particle sizes is in narrow interval 5-50 Å. Some testing methods have shown a separate metal phase is absent at these concentrations and active interaction of metal and polymer is observed.

As PMCS are vastly different from linear polymers in structure and thermal properties and high melting metals are used to stabilize them so it was necessary to use other initial compounds or synthesize them. Also the technological method of thermodestruction and the stage of synthesis of cluster PMCS (CIPMCS) to introduce organometallic compound solution is different for each of them. This compound should have full solubility in synthesis solvent and be fast and clearly decomposed to metal and volatile ligand. The introduction of metals on the intermediate stage of syntheses gives the most effective results because they take part in chemical processes of regrouping and polycondensation. The cyclopentadienyl complexes and carbonyls of metals seem the best to fulfil these demands in the case of CIPMCS. The Ti and Zr complexes syntheses were made as follows. On the first stage sodiumcyclopentadienyl was synthesized from sodium suspension and cyclopentadien in toluene. On the second stage it was transformed into dicyclopentadienylchlorides of Ti and Zr by reaction with metalchlorides in toluene or benzene (inert atmosphere):

PMCS by the traditional method and CIPMCS through organometallic complexes syntheses can be illustrated by following general schemes:

PMCS:

CIPMCS:

CIPMCS syntheses were carried at 250-280 °C and higher dicyclopentadienylchlorides being introduced into fused oligocarbosilanes (dimetildichlorsilane pyrolysis products) mixture at the period when about 10% of Si yet stayed in a Si-Si- fragments. After metals introduction the process speeds up but without any negative by-effect. Si-Si-fragments fully disappear, no insoluble or high fusible products are formed, only high vacuum topping is necessary. To study CIPMCS by nuclear γ -resonance method the model FePMCS was synthesized via ferrumpentacarbonyl with the same method of synthesis.

The cluster polymers average molecular mass were 1200-2500 (gel-penetration chromatography), base skeleton (IR-spectroscopy) like the usual PCS formed by $\equiv\text{Si-C-Si}\equiv$ (1050 and 1350 cm^{-1}) links with hydride $\equiv\text{SiH}$ (2100 cm^{-1}) and methyl $\equiv\text{Si-CH}_3$ (1250 and 1400 cm^{-1}) side substituents at Si-atoms. NMR (^{29}Si)-spectroscopy showed high regularity in CIPMCS structure: groups $\text{HSiC}_3/\text{SiC}_4$ relationship ($\delta = -16$ m.f. and 0 m.f.) is about unity, oxygen containing fragments such as $[\text{SiSi}(\text{C}_2)\text{O}]$ and $[\text{OSi}(\text{C}_2)\text{O}]$ ($\delta = -6,5$ and -22 m.f.) were not discovered. Metals are present in the polymers in the form of cluster particles not

more than 10-50Å in size in the concentration of 0,1-10% (different initial loading) (XSAS, X-ray fluorescence). Preliminary data show that till concentration of 3% metal does not prevent stable spinning of fiber from fused polymer at 250-280 °C. Ceramic yield is up to 75%.

As it can be seen in Table 1 the new (cluster) method of PMCS synthesis provides the same metal introduction without using deficit Si-H - links and more regular polymer structure. It is possible to suppose the evenly dispersed through the polymer clusters act as active centre of polymer molecular embranchment without Si-H-links using. This differs from the method [7], according to which a treating of hidrydesilanes with a catalytic quantity of Ti and Zr complex compounds lead to crosslinking by Si-H links interaction. Certainly the mechanism of cluster (nano-particles) action in the polymer matrix of the PCS-type is a question of series studying.

Oxygenless Curing of Polycarbosilanes

Several methods of this process implementation are known. The most practical now with λ- and e- rays treating [8, 9] are difficult (i.e. expensive) in technology. It is necessary to use unique equipment, flame- and explosion-proof systems, cumbersome schemes for preparing and recovering organic containing gas mixtures. Technological difficulties are not small with the ammonia atmosphere using also [10]. The most valuable from the technological view point would be methods of curing in the atmosphere of pure nitrogen. These methods are based as a rule on unsaturated organic or organoelement compounds introducing into PCS. The heating to the temperature which is higher then the synthesis one cures PCS with this active unsaturated links help [11]. The difficulties are in provision of nearly ideal (molecular) dispersion of additives, their action in rather near temperature interval with high selectivity. Nevertheless this way maybe would be the most effective.

So as the first laboratory results showed that the using of monosilanes with vinyl and allyl substituents such as tetravinyl-, tetraallyl-, trivinylmetyl-, trivinylfenyl- and other monosilanes is very attractive. Advantage and peculiarity on the tetravinylsilane example can be seen from the following scheme:

Unlike other methods there is no gas evolution in this one. It is very important to have dense and regular structure of the ceramic product. Then as reactivity of vinyl groups in the same molecule is different they can react with PCS for example in two stages which is useful for large items. It is handy to cure these items preliminary at not top temperature for some

strengthening in the forming equipment. Then it become possible to remove them into high temperature furnaces to finish the curing and carrying out the heat treating.

An analogous method uses an active amino groups by introducing into PCS some polysilazanes [11] but it is necessary to optimize a residual nitrogen:

One more way of oxygenless curing is now in authors' working out. That is to use cluster (nano-particles) of metals not only for structure stabilizing but for curing as well. They possess a very great surface energy and are possible to tear not only Si-H, but Si-C and C-H links also and to initiate regroup and polycondensation processes at additional thermal treating:

A lot of complicated variants of chemical interaction arise of course, so very fine control of physical and chemical parameters is necessary.

CMC Interface Coatings

This CMC component provides high strength and toughness and long time work at high temperatures in aggressive environment. Its polyfunctionality is illustrated on Fig.3. Massive SiC matrix in the air defends itself by a fine selfcuring film of SiO₂. But it is not enough to defend CMC as a whole. On mechanical force influence microcracks arise in the matrix. They give way for the oxygen into the material right to fiber surface but thin fiber is not possible with the oxide film to defend. More over they move across the fibber and can cut them adhesion between fiber and matrix being strong enough. A fast and even catastrophic brittle destruction of material will follow at rather small load. So it is necessary to have as a minimum two layers on the fiber surface: dense high oxidation resistant (protective) and friable or weak adhesive contributing to local defoliation at crack front-fiber surface point («rheological»). The system fiber-coating-matrix components do not as a rule compatible in thermal expansion coefficients that demands to add in the coating one or more buffer (compensating) layers. The scheme of Fig. 3 shows that there is no protection from initial oxygen in the fiber. No good makes the initial oxygen in the matrix also as its interaction with SiC lead to gas evolution that is harmful for ceramic dense structure:

Attempts to use for high oxidation resistant CMC coatings C, BN, their combinations with TiC and SiC were not successful [12-14 et al.]. High thermostable oxides - Al_2O_3 , Zr_2O_3 - do not hold stable dense structure for a long time at cycle load especially. Practically all of high temperature stable carbides, borides, nitrides, aluminides and silicides are not thermodynamically compatible with SiC and long time oxidation resistant enough. This is why the authors selected as a main research and technology way to use molybdenum disilicide (MoSi_2) for protective layers and polymer precursor SiC - for friable «rheological» layers.

MoSi_2 characteristics are rather well known [15]. The highest oxidation resistance and thermodynamic and thermal expansion compatibility with SiC among refractory compounds, 2000 °C melting point, complementary positive results with W, Ge, Re et al. silicides alloying. Besides it is cheaper and more handy for machining than SiC and Si_3N_4 . Its limitations are more density, lower creep characteristic, fast oxidation process at about 500 °C if pour and microcracks are present. These limitations are difficult to overcome in the matrix and not so difficult in the coating case of using the material. «Rheological» layer for CMC SiC/SiC or SiC or Si_3N_4 is obviously reasonable. Polymer technology provides flexible process control with type and composition of polymer precursors, degree of dilution, number of treating cycles. This in no case excludes the CVD and CVI methods using at some technological stages.

Fig. 3: CMC structure and cracks' spreading scheme
«rheological» layer, 2- protective layer, 3- buffer layer

The experiments were carried out in two types furnaces: with the direct and indirect heating and with the cameras of cold and hot walls accordingly (Fig. 4). Metering and heating means provided 2500 and 1200 °C accordingly both from about $1 \cdot 10^5$ to 1 Pa. Gas mixture preparing system gave possibility to have mixtures of organometallic compounds and metal chlorides with the hydrogen, nitrogen and inert gases of 0,01 - 30% in composition.

Fig. 4: Furnace scheme for interface coatings applying
 1-gas inlet, 2-to vacuum pump outlet, 3- copper water-cooled electrodes, 4- graphite heater, 5- treated sample, 6- silicon carbide heater, 7- steel vessel, 8- vacuum pump

Fig.5: Coating on Nicalon fiber
 1,2–molybdenum: end view ($\times 2980$), side surface ($\times 4000$), 3,4–friable SiC–layer (1% PCS solution, pyrolysis at 1000°C in inert atmosphere) – end view ($\times 2200, \times 17600$)

Fig.6. Coating on SiC/C fiber
 1,2– molybdenum: surface and structure ($\times 6750$), end view ($\times 503$), 3,4– two-layer coating of silicon and molybdenum: side surface ($\times 2020$), end view ($\times 4020$)

CONCLUSIONS

The results support the authors' conception of complex program necessity in working out key components of high oxidation resistant for long time work CMC for civil technical products. New methods for production of oxygenless polymer precursors (PCS and CIPMCS) are an important step in this program. Next one must be the finishing of oxygenless technologically cheap curing methods that will give real possibility to have cheaper oxygenless fiber and to carry active work on interface coatings. This chief line does not exclude parallel experimental work on the all particular subjects of the program.

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